

Spectrophotometric Identification and Determination of *p*-Phenylenediamine Type of Antioxidants in Vulcanised Rubber **

*Anil K. Sircar, A. K. Ghosh, and *D. Banerjee

A method has been proposed for the identification and quantitative determination of antioxidants, derived from *p*-phenylenediamine. It consists in the formation of a highly coloured solution, presumably Wurster's salt, by a reaction of the diamine derivative with acidic permanganate in ethanolic media, and measurement of the absorption with a spectrophotometer. The method has been found suitable for all the four antioxidants studied and also for the *p*-phenylenediamine derivative present as one of the components in a mixed antioxidant.

Derivatives of *p*-phenylenediamine comprise an important class of antioxidants and antiozonants, used in the rubber industry. Several methods are reported in the literature (Burchfield and Judy, *Anal. Chem.*, 1947, 19, 786; Endo, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind., Japan*, 1935, 38, Suppl. binding, 618; Craig, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1937, 9, 56; Zijp, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1957, 76, 313, 317) for identification of these antioxidants along with other amine type of antioxidants. None of these methods, however, is satisfactory for estimation of these antioxidants. Recently, Hilton (*Rubber Age*, 1958, 84, 263; *Anal. Chem.*, 1960, 32, 383) reported a spectrophotometric method for identification and determination of a large number of antioxidants. The method consists in extracting the antioxidant from the rubber sample and formation of an azo dye by addition of a suitable coupling agent. This method was found satisfactory for many antioxidants, but for most of the derivatives of *p*-phenylenediamine, it was otherwise. No method, reported suitable for the determination of this type of antioxidants, has so far been evolved.

The derivatives of *p*-phenylenediamine are known to be oxidised very easily and in ethanolic alkaline solution these form strongly coloured quinone di-imines (Schneider, *Rubber Chem. Technol.*, 1957, 30, 681), whereas in acidic solution Wurster's salts are believed to be formed. Michaelise *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 1981) have examined the essential relationships between structure and stability in the highly coloured oxidation products of *p*-phenylenediamine and its alkyl derivatives; they have pointed out that stable radicals can only be formed when the Wurster's salts have a molecular symmetry sufficiently high for the occurrence of resonance throughout the whole molecule. For this, the benzene ring, the *para* nitrogen atoms, and the four attached groups must lie in one plane, since the contribution of the quinonoid canonical state (II) restricts the rotation of the amino groups.

Substitution of the amino groups of *p*-phenylenediamine enhances the stability of Wurster's salts, but substitution in the benzene ring tends to reduce their stability. The *p*-phenylenediamine

* Present address : National Rubber Manufacturers Ltd., Calcutta-15.

** When this paper was being communicated, a similar work reported by C.L. Hilton (*Anal. Chem.*, 1960, 32, 1554) was noticed which made use of the same principle but differed in experimental details.

type of antioxidants, used in the rubber industry and investigated by the present authors, satisfy these stability requirements, since all the substituents are on the amino-nitrogen and none on the benzene ring. The present method involves the formation of a highly coloured solution (possibly Wurster's salt) from the antioxidant in question by reaction with an oxidising agent, like potassium permanganate or potassium dichromate in acidified ethanol, and measurement of the absorbance with a spectrophotometer.

EXPERIMENTAL

The rubber mix used to ascertain the suitability of the method for the determination of the antioxidants in vulcanised rubber and also for studying the interference, if any, from the common rubber ingredients had the following composition by weight : Raw rubber (smoked sheet) = 100.0 ; ZnO = 5.0 ; stearic acid = 1.5 ; paraffin wax = 2.0 ; carbon black (SRF) = 20.0 ; whiting = 10.0 ; talcum powder = 10.0 ; Dutrex R = 1.0 ; MBTS = 0.5 ; MBT = 0.5 ; ZDC = 0.1 ; sulphur = 3.0 ; antioxidant = 1 to 1.5. The mix was cured at 150° for 30 minutes.

Trade names of the four antioxidants used in the present investigation together with their chemical names and the corresponding wave lengths at maximum absorption are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Trade name.	Chemical name.	$\lambda_{\max}$ (Fig. 1).
Antioxidant 4010	<i>N</i> -Phenyl- <i>N'</i> -cyclohexyl-P	600 $m\mu$
Nonox DPPD	<i>NN'</i> -Diphenyl-P	380
UOP 88	<i>NN'</i> -Dioctyl-P	560
UOP 288	<i>NN'</i> -Dioctyl-P P-denotes <i>p</i> -phenylenediamine.	560

The instrument used was a Hilger Unispek spectrophotometer with a temperature-regulated cell holder and quartz cells having a light path of 1.000 ± 0.005 cm.

Ethanol, 95% glacial acetic acid (reagent grade), and potassium permanganate solution in water ($2.5 \times 10^{-3}M$) were used as reagents.

Procedure.—The absorptivities of the coloured solutions obtained according to the detailed procedure given below were measured at three different states of the antioxidants : (a), (b), (c) (*vide infra*).

(a). *Original Antioxidants in Ethanolic Solution.*—The antioxidant (0.5 g.) was dissolved in ethanol and made to 100 c.c. To the solution (1 c.c.) were added glacial acetic acid (2.5 c.c.) and aqueous $KMnO_4$ (1 c.c., $2.5 \times 10^{-3}M$) (*proportionately smaller amount for lower dilutions*). The colour developed immediately. The volume was made to 25 c.c. with 95% ethanol. The colour remained stable for at least 2 hours. Absorbance was measured soon after dilution taking ethanol containing the same concentration of the reagents in the reference cell of the spectrophotometer.

(b) & (c). *The Antioxidants Extracted from the Uncured and Cured Rubber.*—About 1 g. of the sample of the uncured or the cured mix was taken. The sample to be analysed must be very thinly sheeted in the case of uncured mix or powdered in the case of cured mix by passing through the tight nip of a rubber mixing mill. About 1 g. sample (cured or uncured) was wrapped with a clean filter paper (extracted with acetone), placed in an Underwriter's extraction cup, and extracted with acetone for 12 hours. The extract was distilled till about 20 c.c. of it was left in the flask. The distillate was transferred to a glass basin and evaporated to dryness on a water bath. The residue was redissolved in about 20 c.c. of ethanol and to it were added 3 drops of liquor ammonia and 3 drops of 20% strontium chloride solution in order to precipitate the fatty materials in the mix. The solution was filtered after keeping it overnight in the dark, washed with

ethanol, and made to 50 c.c. with ethanol in a volumetric flask. The above solution (10 c.c.) was treated similarly as in (a) for colour development and absorption measurement. Log absorbance against wave length was plotted and compared with those of the original antioxidants (Fig. 2).

FIG 1.

Absorption spectra of various antioxidants.

FIG 2

Variation of absorbance against concentration.

This will give concentration of the antioxidant present in the extract whereas the wave length at maximum absorption will afford identification of the antioxidant. The visual colour of the oxidised solution of the antioxidants in acidified ethanol is also characteristic and provides good indication for its identification.

Table II records the results of analysis of the antioxidants in the uncured and the cured mixes.

TABLE II

Stocks containing	Colour in acetic acid.	Colour developed after oxidation.	λ_{max}	% Added (X).	% Found (Y).		Diff. (X-Y).	
					Uncured mix (A).	Cured mix (B).	X-A.	X-B.
Antioxidants 4010	Faint blue	Ultramarine blue	600m μ	1.20	1.08	1.05	0.12	0.15
					1.09	1.03	0.11	0.17
					1.11	1.04	0.09	0.16
Nonox DPPD	Nil	Ocean blue	380	1.61	1.58	1.52	0.03	0.09
					1.56	1.50	0.05	0.11
					1.58	1.49	0.03	0.12
UOP 88	Red	Red colour deepens	560	1.35	1.31	1.28	0.04	0.07
					1.30	1.25	0.05	0.10
					1.32	1.27	0.03	0.08
UOP 288	Do	Do	560	1.00	0.96	0.95	0.04	0.05
					0.97	0.95	0.03	0.05
					0.93	0.91	0.07	0.09

DISCUSSION

The results in Tables I and II indicate the feasibility of the present method in ascertaining the presence of a *p*-phenylenediamine derivative in an unknown sample of antioxidant as also of its identification provided that the absorption data are known from a previous study. The antioxidants present in an uncured or cured mix can also be identified and determined after extraction.

In the present study the antioxidants were determined within about 6 to 7% except in the case of antioxidant 4010, where the differences between quantity added and that found were higher (10 to 15%). The difference is higher in the case of the cured stock than in the uncured one, and the antioxidant found is always less than the quantity added. This is not unexpected as some antioxidant may be lost during extraction. Also there is a possibility of some quantity of antioxidant being consumed during curing at a high temperature; the loss by consumption explains higher figures in the case of cured stocks than uncured ones in the last two columns of Table II. It has also been observed that the usual compounding ingredients do not have appreciable effect on the determination*. Though analysis of the antioxidants is given in the range of 1 to 1.6% (Table II), the method is applicable to a much lower quantity.

An experiment with Acroflex CD (a mixture of phenyl- β -nappthylamine and diphenyl- p -phenylenediamine, DPPD) indicates the applicability of the present method to a mixture containing a p -phenylenediamine type of antioxidants as one of the components. The measured percentage

FIG. 3
Effect of $KMnO_4$ conc. on the absorption spectrum
of antioxidant 4010.

Concentration of $KMnO_4 = 2.5 \times 10^{-3} M$.
(A) 1.0 c.c. of $KMnO_4/25$ c.c. (B) 2.0 c.c. of $KMnO_4/25$ c.c.
(C) 25 c.c. of $KMnO_4/25$ c.c.

of DPPD (36%) agrees well with the actual (35%). It seems that the colour formation, described above, is specific to this type. Other antioxidants like Nonox D, Nonox B, Nonox BL, Nonox HFN, Flectol H, Antioxidant MB, Nonox EXN, Nonox WSL, and Nonox KSM, do not give appreciable coloration with acidified permanganate solution. Even p -phenylenediamine itself does not exhibit any distinct colour under the specified condition (a yellow colour was obtained deepening with time). It was noted that ethanolic solutions of DPPD type of antioxidants, as found with a sample of antioxidant 4010, were oxidised by air even in stoppered bottles and developed the characteristic coloration of the oxidised samples on acidification alone. Further oxidation with permanganate changed the colour to violet and shifted the maximum absorption to shorter wave length, as was also observed in the case of oxidation with a large amount of permanganate (Fig. 3).

Thanks are due to Prof. S. K. Mukherjee and Prof. S. R Palit for encouragement during the course of this investigation.

* It may be noted here that the procedure of Hilton (*loc. cit.*) using cupric acetate as the oxidising agent is not applicable in presence of thiuram disulphide and thiocarbamate type of accelerators because of the formation of coloured cupric salts.